

The Contemporary Trends in Advertising Services Global Market

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ABSTRACT. One of the powerful driving forces in any business is advertising. Business internationalization contributes to the constitution of the global market of advertising services that also is digitalized. In this article, the authors aim to uncover and explore the contemporary trends in the global market of advertising services, under globalization and digitalization socio-economic megatrends. *Methodology and Results:* Leaned upon the evolutionary approach to the global market of advertising services, and the analysis of relevant statistical data, the authors have systematized the main trends observed in global advertising services market and provided explanations for these trends. They also have identified and analyzed the particular directions within these general trends. Furthermore, the authors have paid attention to the shifts in global market of advertising services produced by the COVID-19 pandemic crisis and offered recommendations which, alongside the outcomes of the article, may help businesses to develop their strategies in line with the revealed and systematized trends and particular directions in order to become more competitive at the contemporary global market of advertising services. In this context a concept of performance advertising has been introduced.

KEYWORDS: Contemporary Trend, Global Market, Advertising Service, Performance Advertising
JEL Classification: F0, M3

1. Introduction

The success of any business much depends on its promotion, including through advertising channels. The processes of economic liberalization, which have now covered nearly all countries of the world, have contributed to the fact that these countries are rapidly integrating into the world economy and, therefore, into the world market of advertising services. This fact, in turn, contributes to the constitution of the world economy and its markets as global. Besides, the application of informational and telecommunication technologies contribute to the development of the world market of advertising services as the global one but in a virtual dimension, adding it to the traditional physical dimension. Therefore, in order to remain competitive, contemporary economic agents should follow the trends in the global market of advertising services.

The purpose of this article is to highlight and explore the trends on the world market of advertising services, the latter being in globalization (Rotaru 2014, 532-541) and digitalization, to help increasing business competitiveness. The global advertising market is a sphere of international advertising activity associated with systematic sales and purchases of advertising services, organizationally based on global networks of advertising agencies. The global advertising market emerged and is currently developing in the process of deepening and expanding the process of economic integration, the activities of transnational and international companies, and the evolution of the world economy and international trade as the global ones. Today we can state that this market is huge - in 2021, the world's advertising expenditure was 705 billion US dollars, which is about 0.77% of the world GDP (Zenith 2021, 1).

Methodology and results. Our analysis of statistical data from world reports relevant to the present research, as well as the international investigations in the given field allowed the

application of the evolutionary approach to the global advertising services market. As a result, we can sustain that there are many trends that determine the contemporary development of the world advertising services market. Grouping them together, we can distinguish the following six basic current trends:

1. Continued globalization of the world advertising market, its further expansion and global consolidation.
2. Growth of volume of international advertising market (increasing investment in advertising).
3. The process of concentration of revenues and market share.
4. Changing channels and means of delivering advertising to consumers.
5. Shifts in the global advertising services market caused by the COVID-19 pandemic.
6. The trend of reducing the overall effectiveness of advertising.

The process of exploring the highlighted trends allows us to identify the particular directions within each of these major trends.

2. Continued Globalization of the World Advertising Market, its Further Expansion and Global Consolidation

The modern advertising market is an integral part of the world economy, to the formation of which transnational companies make the most significant contribution. They work in the advertising market on a global scale, contributing to the accelerated development of the global mass media and the global exchange of information (Nikonova *et al.* 59).

The increasing globalization of industries such as consumer goods and automobiles makes advertisers to change their creative and spending strategies to reach buyers in countries with growing disposable incomes. The transnational companies develop clear, simple and consistent marketing messages that are applicable to different cultures. The experts point out the global nature of the advertising market - all regions of the world economy contribute to the global advertising spending. The largest share is that of North America (42%), the Asia-Pacific region (29.6%), and Western Europe (17.4%) (Zenith 2021, 6).

At the same time, the globalization of advertising services requires multinational companies to study more deeply the cultural differences and peculiarities, including the linguistic ones, of their target (local) markets. Thus, for example, as researchers from the Stern School noted, the advertising campaign under the name "Got Milk?" of the American Dairy Association, having been very successful in the US, did not work in Mexico because the phrase that was the basis of their promotional axis, when translated into Spanish, appeared as "Are You Lactating?" (Hirsh 2022), acquiring an offensive connotation. Quite often, the humorous advertising campaigns might work in one country, while not fitting into a cultural environment in another country. In this context, it is worth mentioning that not only verbal messages, but also non-verbal ones should obviously be treated with a certain precautions, for example, the use of some symbols and colors. Thus, many tropical countries associate the color green with danger, which is not the case in the US or European countries. The red color is associated with weddings and happiness in China (Hirsh 2022), India, and some Asian countries but may have a different perception in the European region.

The subsequent analysis leads us to highlight two opposite directions in the evolution of advertising services under the impact of globalization. *The first* refers to the need to develop clear, simple, uniform advertising messages with culturally neutral content that can be understood identically in any local market. *The second* direction forms itself under more in-depth localization of marketing strategies. The latter results in maximum adaptation of both products and advertising messages to the native culture of the targeted consumers. The

transnational companies, which have developed successful global brands, can show us examples of the successful combination of both directions in their advertising messages, increasing their completeness on the global market. Thus, *McDonald's* corporation, on the one hand, has launched clear, simple and coherent messages on the global advertising market, which relate to different cultures in a uniform way. On the other hand, it has revised its product lines “to feature healthier items and others geared to local markets -- such as wine in France and sushi in Asian countries” (Hirsh 2022). It also demonstrates through its advertising messages loyalty to the cultures of target markets by using ingredients specific to those cultures, for example, avoiding pork in the market of Arab countries and beef in the Indian market.

However, increased access to cable and satellite television, as well as broadband Internet, are also establishing global links between nations and common expectations of their consumers. This has worked particularly to the advantage of airlines, apparel manufacturers and other advertisers targeting a global audience. This allows us to continue the logic of the first direction within the globalization of the world advertising market mentioned above, by arguing that effective advertising through clear, simple, culturally neutral and standardized messages result in their effective perception, and can create new demand in new markets, influencing changes in habits and lifestyles of purchase at the local markets. In doing so, the overseas teenagers and young adults have turned American brands like *Levi's*, *Nike*, *McDonald's* and *Marlboro* into global brands (Hirsh 2022).

Another trend, which has its echo in history, is to capitalize on events of global significance such as the Olympic Games to boost the companies' brands with an international audience. The bright examples here is the electronics manufacturer *LG* when the games were held in South Korea and wireless carrier *China Mobile* when the event was held in Beijing (Hirsh 2022).

3. Growth of Volume of International Advertising Market (Increasing Investment in Advertising)

According to global advertising agency *Zenith*, in 2010, global advertising spending was approximately 393 billion US dollars. In 2021, the figure increased to 688 billion US dollars (Zenith 2021, 8). Thus, the increase was 175%! Prognosis is that by the end of the 2020s, the figure will exceed 1 trillion US dollars (Grous 2022).

This trend can be explained by the fact, on the one hand, of the globalization of the international market of advertising services, on the other hand, by its digitalization. Thus, global digital expenditures showed explosive growth dynamics, starting with the year 2000, and demonstrate a constant increase, along with global traditional advertising expenditures, towards the year 2030 (Grous 2022).

4. The Process of Concentration of Revenues and Market Share

Currently, the global advertising market is dominated by a number of transnational corporations that have collected the most considerable part of the advertising business, which allows them to control a significant share of the global advertising market (Nikonova *et al*, 59). Table 1 shows the ten largest advertising agencies, by revenue, which are particularly sizable in the global advertising services market.

Table 1. The world's 10 largest advertising agencies by revenue in 2021

Advertising agency	Headquarter	Revenue, billion US dollars
<i>WPP</i>	London	17.6
<i>Omnicom Group</i>	New York	14.3
<i>Publicis Groupe</i>	Paris	13.9
<i>Accenture's Accenture Interactive (now - Accenture Song)</i>	New York	12.5
<i>The Interpublic Group of Companies</i>	New York	10.2
<i>Dentsu Group Inc</i>	Tokyo	9.9
<i>PwC's PwC Digital Services</i>	New York	8.9
<i>Deloitte's Deloitte Digital</i>	New York	8.7
<i>Hakuhodo DY Holdings</i>	Tokyo	7.5
<i>IBM Corp.'s IBM iX</i>	New York	6.4

Source: adapted by the authors based on Statista (2022)

The process of income concentration in hands of the small group of international companies could be explained, first, by the fact that these companies are able to capitalize on both directions within globalization, considered by us above. They develop global, transnational and local messages appropriate, on the one hand, to consumers of advertising services from the global market, on the other hand, to those from local markets. In the research (Siscan 2021) global, local and transnational approaches to marketing communications are discussed in the light of neuromarketing, highly used by the leading advertising companies. Secondly, the process of income concentration in the global advertising services market may also be explained by the fact that the leading companies succeed to capitalize thanks to digitization of their international business. Thus, the analysis of the distribution of revenues and the market share from digital advertising during the years 2016-2023, so including forecasts, based on the data of the company eMarketer, shows us the concentration of global revenues from e-advertising at five leading companies, such as *Google* (31.5%), *Facebook* (14.3%), *Alibaba* (6.2%), *Tencent* (1.9%) and *Amazon* (0.8%), in 2016 (Cramer-Flood 2021). Summing it up, we can notice that in the reference year the global market share of digital advertising services belonging to those five companies was 54.7%. Further study and calculations lead us to the conclusion that the total share of the revenues of the targeted companies is in increase, intensifying the trend of concentration of revenues and global market share. Thus, in 2020, the share of total revenues obtained by *Google* (27.5%), *Facebook* (22.3%), *Alibaba* (8.6%), *Tencent* (2.9%) and *Amazon* (5.2%) constituted already 66.5% of the total global digital advertising spend. Estimates for the year 2023 show us the market share of *Google* 27.5%, *Meta Platforms* (formerly Facebook) – 25.2%, *Alibaba* – 9.5%, *Tencent* - 3.1% and *Amazon* - 7.1% (Cramer-Flood 2021). Thus, the simple calculation shows that the cumulative global digital advertising services market share of these five companies will increase to 72.4% by the year 2023.

5. Changing Channels and Means of Delivering Advertising to Consumers

The analysis of the global market of advertising services through the lens of channels and means of delivery of advertising to consumers shows us that there is a redistribution of expenses in the direction of digital advertising. Logambal has argued in his research, dedicated to emerging trends in advertising, that a paradigm shift took place last decades. It conditioned the change of channels, means and modes of advertising. "There were days when producers and manufacturers depended only on radios, newspapers, and pamphlets to advertise their products

it was only until the late nineties when digital media crawled in and in early 2000 seen it spread its wings" (Logambal 2016, 22).

The analysis of statistical data, provided by the company *Raconteur Media* (Raconteur Media 2021) through the optics of the evolution of expenses for advertising channels on the global market, allows us to highlight the following trends. Spending on newspaper advertising was increasing until 2007, spending on magazine advertising saw growth until 2008, and spending on TV advertising saw growth until 2014. Spending on search advertising began to rise suddenly in the early 2000s, and spending on social media and online cinema advertising began to increase from the year 2010.

The comparative analysis of the data for the years 2010 and 2021, provided by the advertising agency *Zenith* (Zenith 2021), allows us to draw the following conclusions. In 2010, television was a priority channel for ad spending, accounting for 48.1 billion US dollars, which constituted, according to our calculations, 37.7% of total ad spending in the global market. Newspapers took the second position in the ranking, with a share of 20.9%, but online advertising services were only in the 3rd place, constituting 16.8% of total expenses (see table 2). However, the data from 2021 show us that the situation has changed radically. Spending on online advertising services has already reached 405.3 billion US dollars, which constituted 58.9% of the total spending on advertising channels in the global market. The expenses for television knew the second position in the ranking, having the weight of only 24.8% in the total expenses. The placement of advertising in newspapers has already reached the 4th place (4.3%), letting the third position to the street advertising channel with a share of 5% of the respective total expenses. According to estimates made by the leading company in global media investments *GroupM*, in its report edition of June 2022, digital advertising will reach 73% of the global industry's revenues (GroupM 2022).

Table 2. The evolution of advertising channels through the prism of expenses

Advertising channels	2010			2021		
	Expenditure, billion US dollars	Share of total expense %	Ranking	Expenditure, billion US dollars	Share of total expense%	Ranking
<i>Newspapers</i>	82,2	20,9	2	29,7	4,3	4
<i>Magazines</i>	38,1	9,7	4	17,5	2,5	6
<i>Radio</i>	28,6	7,3	5	27,9	4	5
<i>Television</i>	148,1	37,7	1	171	24,8	2
<i>Cinema</i>	2,1	0,5	7	2,3	0,3	7
<i>Outdoor</i>	27,5	7	6	34,3	5	3
<i>Online</i>	66,2	16,8	3	405,3	58,9	1

Source: Adapted and calculated by the authors based on data from Zenith (2021)

As the particular directions within the considered trend of the changing investment priorities in advertising channels in favour to the online advertising, we can notice, first, that the share of social networks increased in the total spending for Internet advertising from 2.06 billion US dollars in 2010 to 148.8 billion US dollars in 2021 (Zenith 2021, 8). Secondly, online advertising is absolutely dominated by mobile ad spend, not "desktop advertising", although 10 years ago it was the other way around. Thus, in 2010, desktop advertising constituted 65.746 billion US dollars, but mobile advertising registered only 501 million US dollars. Starting with 2017, in which spending on mobile advertising for the first time surpassed spending on desktop advertising, already constituting 127.4 billion compared to 89.7 billion US dollars and establishing itself as a trend. In 2021, spending on mobile advertising was 287.9 billion, but for desktop advertising - 117.4 billion US dollars in current prices (ibid.).

6. Shifts in the Global Advertising Services Market Caused by the Covid-19 Pandemic

The change in the global advertising services market that took place due to the COVID-19 pandemic could be expressed through a grouping of several particular trends here. *The first one* relates to the fact that the pandemic has completely disrupted consumer behavior. For many consumers, who preferred to buy goods in a physical reality, the need for online shopping appeared (Zenith 2021, 1). According to a study conducted by the international research company *Kantar Millward Brown*, during self-isolation, people began to spend 63% more time behind the screens of personal computers and smartphones (Mikriukov *et al.* 2021, 147). As a result, companies have continued their increased investment in the digital transformation of its advertising. Several brands have started to adapt their advertising campaigns to the current situation and modify their promotional message. This constituted *the second particular trend*. For example, *KFC* released an ad in 2019 in which people licked their fingers after eating chicken. The company received 163 complaints from UK residents. People called it irresponsible and said it could spread COVID-19, so *KFC* representatives suspended such promotional messages. Confectionery brand *Hershey* ran an advertising centered on hugs and handshakes. Later, the company replaced its video with product image frames, accompanied by voice acting and text. This is how the brand representatives reacted to the corona virus outbreak and WHO recommendations to reduce contact with others. *Burger King* created two videos about the increased hygiene requirements at its units (Nasonova 2020, 106-107).

Having analysed the situation through the lens of spending on advertising services, based on data from the *Zenith* agency, we can notice that these spending, in current prices, decreased in 2020 compared to 2019 by 3.8%, but registered an unprecedented increase in 2021 by 15.6 %, (Zenith 2021, 9), first of all, thanks to electronic advertising.

During the pandemic, the advertising budget planning strategy changed. According to a survey conducted by the agency *PRT Edelman Affiliate*, among marketing directors and media directors of large international companies, about 40% of respondents said that they had done budget planning ad hoc, and 30% switched to monthly planning. Almost 60% of respondents reported that they stopped outdoor advertising during the pandemic, 38.5% reduced spending on BTL, 34% on traditional TV, 25% on commercial marketing and 22% on radio advertising. Among the priority digital channels for promotion, advertisers identified social media marketing (66%), contextual advertising (53%), blogger activations (44%), advertising banners (37%), and digital PR (31%) (Chervonsky 2020).

International experts in the field of advertising services emphasize the growing role of social networks in the promotion of global products and services. According to the online survey, organized by the researchers Mikriucov V. and Axenova A., 56.5% of respondents reported that they began to spend more time on social networks and the Internet during the pandemic (Mikriukov *et al.*, 148). Business people, who actively capitalized on the different forms and new technologies in digital advertising, caught the trend. In doing so, the special attention they pay to gamification of the content of promotional messages, the development of AR technologies, CTV advertising, and active collaboration with opinion leaders (influencers).

Proceeding from the fact that maintaining consumer attention both in the sense of time and under high pressure of global competition is an actual issue for business people, creativity comes to the foreground. Alongside with the new technologies, advertisers have also used the corona virus theme for advertising purposes, updating it to the needs of the audience. Thus, the advertising and communications company *BBDO* developed in the early days of the pandemic a series of videos for its clients to educate the Internet audience about the corona virus, as well as showing what measures they should take to protect themselves against the virus. By doing so, the company supported the current trend and demonstrated care towards the consumer, which did not go unnoticed (Mikriukov *et al.* 149).

7. The Trend of Reducing the Overall Effectiveness of Advertising

This trend manifests itself in two ways. On the one hand, young people are less inclined to use mass media such as TV, newspapers, magazines, radio, which dominated the market in the last century. According to experts from the Hong Kong financial company *Velotrade*, "more young consumers are indifferent to traditional media" (Velotrade 2023). Obviously, the effectiveness of advertising companies using this kind of media certainly goes down with a decrease in their coverage.

The youth of today, especially Generation Z, born between 1997 and 2012, use the Internet as the main source of information. Older generations are trying to keep up. Consequently, the places where a typical contemporary consumer, especially among young people, spends a decent part of their day are news sites, blogs, video hosting, and social networks. Marketers are well aware of this shift what is reflected by the fact that online advertising spend increased 6 times in the decade between 2010 and 2021 (See Table 2).

However, in this area, not everything is as smooth as it seems at first glance. Currently, the Internet information space is really oversaturated. Against this background, the visibility and impact of advertising on people are falling. Researchers at *eMarketer*, a market research company, stated in concern: "Most consumers now proactively avoid advertising, whether by using ad blockers, paying for ad-free digital media experiences, or skipping ads" (Insider Intelligence & eMarketer, 2021). Statistics based on user surveys really paint a disappointing picture. According to the social media marketing and management platform *Hootsuite* report, an average of 37% of respondents from 47 countries used ad blockers, in particular in China - 47%, in Germany - 38.9%, Russia - 38.7%, Sweden - 37.6 %, France - 36.2%, Romania - 34.7%, USA - 34.2%, UK - 32%, Japan - 19.9% (Digital 2022, 271).

Our analysis of the age and sex composition of users who use ad blockers shows that most of them are among men aged 16-24 years (39.4% on average across countries) and 25-34 years old (43.2%), in contrast to men aged 55-64 (34.3%) (Digital 2022, 272). That is, some of the most economically active segments of the population neglect Internet advertising.

The reasons why the surveyed users ignore advertising are as follows: "there are too many ads" - 62.1%, "ads get in the way" - 55.3%, "ads aren't relevant to me" - 40.8% (Digital 2022, 273). Another research in this context even increases the picture. Thus, according to the Digital consumer research report created by the Customer Collaboration Platform *Bulbshare*, 74% of consumers feel bombarded with ads, 63% of Generation Z use ad blockers to avoid online adverts. As the experts sustain, "they feel overwhelmed by the number of adverts they see daily". More than that, advertising fatigue and disillusionment has gone so far that 84% of those born between 1997 and 2012 have lost faith in influencers - TV stars, TikTok, Youtube, Twitter, Instagram, Facebook, who usually have a large and loyal audience (Marketing Beat 2022).

The contemporary marketers are eager to find the solutions to make the advertising services more effective. In this context, one of the studies conducted in the USA, has reflected some suggestions given by the respondents as follows. When asked what improvements would make them pay more attention to online ads, American respondents, especially Millennials (ages 18-34), recommended to make the ad funny (40%), to make it entertaining (32%), to add stunning graphics (19%), to feature a sexy man or woman in advertising (10%). Besides, the Millennials said they would pay attention to online ads if they were interactive, preferred it more if compared with any other age group (21% vs. 9% of those ages 35+) (MediaPost 2014).

Conclusion

Advertising is the driving force of any business. The deep internationalization of economic affairs, on the one hand, and the scientific-technologic progress with its ICTs, on the other hand, contribute to the development of the world market of advertising services as global and

digitalized. This fact, in its own turn, calls forth numbers of trends on the global advertising market that can be grouped in six trends as follows: continued globalization of the world advertising market; increasing investment in advertising; concentration of revenues and market share; changing channels and means of delivering advertising to consumers, shifts in the global advertising services market caused by the COVID-19 pandemic (Rotaru 2020, 71-82) and reducing the overall effectiveness of advertising.

Each trend contains some particular directions. The list is not completed, but proceeding from the preliminary research outcomes, there may be drawn some recommendations for increasing competitiveness of economic agents in the contemporary global environment. Globalization of the world market for advertising services makes it especially significant for the advertisers to find its niche, to maintain it under the high intensive global completion, to target as precise as possible its target audience worldwide, to assess correct the communication and promotion channels, including from the cross-cultural perspective, to allocate a budget reported in percentage correct and sufficient for promotion, to switch to the new channels based on the new technologies, to learn new methods in digital advertising, and to make the advertising even more creative, interactive and entertaining. Communicating messages to the target audience is as effective as the dissemination and communication channel is properly selected. Each category of consumer, depending on the criteria according to which it has been established, is receptive only to certain communication channels, i.e. (Petcu 2013, 4) their correct assessment means that the message reaches the consumer directly, thereby increasing the chances that the consumer will react favorably and achieve the act of purchase.

One more recommendation to add is as follows. The advertising may become much more effective if the contemporary postmodern megatrend is further exploited in the sense of organizing the advertising in the form of *performance*, and in case of global market – *digital performance*. This means that a potential consumer is involved in a particular situation or a series of situations designed by marketers, or even together with the consumers, and by their participation in a certain action a product or a service is being advertised. Unlike the involvement of the superstars, famous bloggers and other influencers, *performance advertising* deals with the ordinary consumers. It is based on the desire of each person to become “an influencer.” Additionally, this approach will meet the requirements of the contemporary consumers from both considerable categories – Generation Z and the Millennials– to make the advertising more creative, interactive and entertaining.

References

- Chervonsky, A. 2020. *Business vo vremia pandemii: kak korporatsii raspredelyaiut reklamnyi budjety v novih realiyah* [online] Available at <https://vc.ru/marketing/127297-biznes-vo-vremya-pandemii-kak-korporacii-raspredelyaiut-reklamnye-byudzhetny-v-novyh-realiyah> [Accessed 12 October 2022].
- Cramer-Flood, E. 2021. *Duopoly still rules the global digital ad market, but Alibaba and Amazon are on the prowl* [online] Available at: <https://www.insiderintelligence.com/content/duopoly-still-rules-global-digital-ad-market-alibaba-amazon-on-prowl>. Accessed 20 September 2022.
- Digital 2022. *Global Overview Report. Hootsuite & We are social*. [online] Available at: <https://datareportal.com/reports/digital-2022-global-overview-report>. Accessed 11 June 2023.
- GroupM. 2022. *This Year Next Year* [online] Available at: https://d2ksis2z2ke2jq.cloudfront.net/uploads/2022/06/GroupM_TYNY_June2022.pdf. Accessed 7 October 2022.
- Grous N., 2022. *Global Digital Advertising Appears Poised for Significant Growth*. ARK Invest, February 08 [online] Available at: <https://ark-invest.com/articles/analyst-research/global-digital-advertising-appears-poised-for-significant-growth/>. Accessed 15 September 2022.
- Hirsh, L. 2022. *Globalization's Impact in Advertising* [online] Available at: <https://smallbusiness.chron.com/globalizations-impact-advertising-71068.html>. Accessed 10 October 2022.

- Insider Intelligence & eMarketer, 2021, July 22. Consumer Attitudes Toward Digital Advertising. [online] Available at: <https://www.insiderintelligence.com/content/consumer-attitudes-toward-digital-advertising-2021>. Accessed 11 June 2023.
- Logambal, R. 2016. "Emerging Trends in Advertising." In *International Conference on Service Marketing - Talking the Show Abroad (ICSMTSA-2016)*. IOSR, *Journal of Business and Management*, 20-22 [online] Available at: <https://www.iostjournals.org/iosr-jbm/papers/Conf-ICSMTSA/Volume%201/6.%2020-22.pdf>. Accessed 2 October 2022.
- Marketing Beat. 2022. May, 30. "Skip this ad? Generation Z are ignoring ads at all costs". [online] Available at: <https://www.marketing-beat.co.uk/2022/05/30/young-people-ads-generation-z/>. Accessed 12 June 2023.
- MediaPost. 2014, February 25. "Four of Five American Consumers Ignore Online Ads Most Frequently." [online] Available at: <https://www.mediapost.com/publications/article/220101/>. Accessed 12 June 2023.
- Mikriukov, V., Axenova A., 2021. "Kreativnyi podhody v reklame tovarov i uslug vo vremea pandemii COVID-19." *Gosudarstvenoe upravlenie*. *Elektroni vestnik* 86: 141-157.
- Nasonova, I. 2020. "Mirovoi riнок reklam 2020: vliyanie Covid-19." *Ekonomika i Business: teoria i praktika* 5-2, 63: 105-107.
- Nikonova, Y., and Kanieva M. 2014. "Inovatsionnye tendentsii na sovremenom reklamnom rinke." In *Meždunarodnyj naučno-issledovatel'skij* 11,30: 58-59.
- Petcu, Cristian Vasile. 2013. "Historical and canonical reflections on the Church's philanthropic work." *International Journal of Orthodox Theology* 4:4.
- Raconteur Media. 2021. *Content for Business Decision-Makers. Ad Evolution*. [online] Available at: <https://www.raconteur.net/infographics/ad-evolution/>. Accessed 20 September 2022.
- Rotaru, Ioan-Gheorghe. 2014. "Globalization and its effect on religion." *Jurnalul Libertății de Conștiință* 1(1): 532-541.
- Rotaru, Ioan-Gheorghe. 2020. "Spiritual lessons observed through the Coronavirus Crisis." *Dialogo. Issue of Modern Man* 6(2): 71-82.
- Siscan, Z. 2021. "Neuromarketing Strategic Engineering: Global, Local, and Transnational." In: Xu J., Duca G., Ahmed S., Márquez F., Hajiyevev A. (eds.), *Proceedings of the Fourteenth International Conference on Management Science and Engineering Management*, Vol. 2. Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing Volume 1191, Springer International Publishing, 392-404 [online] Available at: <https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007%2F978-3-030-49889-4>.
- Statista. 2022. *Leading advertising agency groups worldwide in 2021, by revenue (in billion U.S. dollars)* [online] Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/273879/revenue-of-the-worlds-largest-agency-companies/>. Accessed 15 September 2022.
- Velotrade. 2023, February 3. *Global Advertising Trends: Data You Should Know*. [online] Available at: <https://www.velotrade.com/blog/global-advertising-trends-data/>. Accessed 12 June 2023.
- Zenith. 2021. *Advertising Expenditure Forecasts Report. December*. [pdf]. Zenith. Available at: https://s3.amazonaws.com/media.mediapost.com/uploads/Advertising_Expenditure_ForecastsDecember_2021_0N69DuK.pdf. Accessed 20 September 2022.